

Humanity in the Womb of History

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What we do not understand can be frightening... But when one is troubled by the reality of this world, it can be comforting to consider other possibilities, even if those possibilities disturb us, so strong is the desire to escape the tyranny of consciousness and the narrow boundaries of our perceptions, to unlock the prisons of thought in which we trap ourselves, all in hope that a better world, or a better version of ourselves, perhaps, may lie on the other side of the door.

Trade Minister Tagomi, *The Man in the High Castle* (Bucksey)

If one gauges a society's future by the pronouncements of its artists, scientists, and intellectuals, then of late ours would appear bleak. Both Stephen Hawking and Noam Chomsky have recently warned that right now is the most dangerous time our species has ever faced, considering the hydra of existential threats that confront us, including climate change, soil depletion, epidemic disease, acidification of oceans, nuclear war, and mass species extinction (see for example Hawking). Citing among a number of other troubling developments the election of Donald J. Trump in the United States, the Bulletin of Atomic Scientists has moved the Doomsday Clock to two and a half minutes to midnight, the closest it has been since the first hydrogen bomb tests by the Americans and Soviets in 1953 (Bulletin). Writing in the Summer 2017 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, Gerardo Ceballos, Paul Ehrlich, and Rodolfo Dirzo report that

Earth is experiencing a huge episode of population declines and extirpations, which will have negative cascading consequences on ecosystem functioning and services vital to sustaining civilization. We describe this as a “biological annihilation” to highlight the current magnitude of Earth’s ongoing sixth major extinction event ... and the window for effective action is very short, probably two or three decades at most. All signs point to ever more powerful assaults on biodiversity in the next two decades, painting a dismal picture of the future of life, including human life.

Whatever the veracity of these prognostications, the new millennium appears to have ushered a script change in the collective mind of Western society. Few events have imprinted more powerfully upon the psyche of millennials than the terrorist attacks of September 11, 2001, and the global financial collapse of 2007-2008, the ensuing wreckage of which has fanned flames of neo-fascism across Europe and the Americas. It

has now become easier, Slavoj Žižek observed, to imagine apocalypse than a truly different and better future.

And yet, the new millennium simultaneously presents an alternate horizon in which humanity figures out how to work together as a species to eliminate poverty, restore the health of our ecosystem, and as one race set off to explore the reaches of inner and outer space. With the growth of the Internet, we appear to be in the incipient stages of developing a global neocortex, sharing more information and connecting more minds with each passing day. This spectacular tool, however, presents the potential for great evil as well as great good, and for dividing as well as uniting us. In any case, it requires that we bring the best of our humanity to the table.

In his 2016 encyclical *Laudato Si*, Pope Francis addressed the need to “care for our common home” by delving into “the heart of what it is to be human,” and by reference to Saint Francis of Assisi, who spoke to flowers and loved small creatures as brothers and sisters. Speaking to a joint session of the United States Congress that September, Francis called upon Americans to follow the example of Thomas Merton, the Trappist monk who, standing one day in downtown Louisville, awoke “from a dream of separateness. He looked at all the people on the street and said that there were no strangers” (Pope Francis, “Visit”; see also Ellsberg). These words forge a tenuous link between American culture and the *Unio Mystica*, an uncanny phenomenology attuned to the oneness of humanity and all life on earth, of which vestiges may be traced to the roots of the Western philosophical tradition.

Through their *skole* and annual rites at Eleusis, the ancient Athenians institutionalized pedagogies of consciousness change. While recognizing their society to be flawed, these forebears also believed their nature to be Promethean. The early *skole*, as Joseph Pieper argues, were not schools as we understand them today but religious cults devoted to the worship of *leisure*, a capacity considered to be at once both human and superhuman, allowing men and women to reach beyond themselves and achieve transcendence (Pieper 28). Beginning in fear and even terror, the Mysteries ultimately revealed this transcendental dimension. Featuring the word *digenes*, conveying the sense of “twice-born,” accounts tell of a world suddenly transformed from an inert pile of matter into a living, ethereal tissue binding all of humanity and nature (cf. Wasson, Hofmann and Ruck 26, 47; see also Huston Smith 18). Wrote Cicero:

Though Athens brought forth numerous divine things, yet she never created anything nobler than those sublime Mysteries through which we became gentler and have advanced from a barbarous and rustic life to a more civilized one, so that we not only live more joyfully but also die with a better hope. (Qtd. in Wasson, Hofmann and Ruck 142)

Against the background of an evolutionary model of consciousness, contemporary forms of life — principally related to our economic system, neurochemistry, and habits of digital technology usage — constitute phenomenological curricula that nurture atavistic aspects of our humanity and contribute to the hydra of maladies now threatening most life

on earth. With reference to the traditions of ancient Greece, deliberately entertained curricula of consciousness might aid us in the work of self-transformation that appears necessary if humanity is to deliver itself through the gathering storms.

1. A Circuit Model of Consciousness

[O]ur normal waking consciousness, rational consciousness as we call it, is but one special type of consciousness, whilst all about it, parted from it by the filmiest of screens, there lie potential forms of consciousness entirely different. We may go through life without suspecting their existence; but apply the requisite stimulus, and at a touch they are there in all their completeness, definite types of mentality which probably somewhere have their field of application and adaptation. No account of the universe in its totality can be final which leaves these other forms of consciousness quite disregarded. How to regard them is the question, for they are so discontinuous with ordinary consciousness. Yet they may determine attitudes though they cannot furnish formulas, and open a region though they fail to give a map. At any rate, they forbid a premature closing of our accounts with reality.

William James, *The Varieties of Religious Experience*

All that we can know of self and the world must pass through the lens of consciousness. Human beings possess the most highly realized form of consciousness of which we are aware, our brains being capable of ten to the power of 2.7 million connections, more than the number of stars in the known universe (Wilson, *Prometheus*. See also Wilson, “Techniques”). Yet we share our most basic neurocircuitry with the first creatures to emerge from the oceans hundreds of millions of years ago. We are half animal and half spirit, Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Hyde.

Although the mind has throughout history demonstrated a capacity to both perceive and exhibit the mystical, modern humanity is by and large conditioned to inhabit what may be called *waking* or *rational consciousness*. Because the immediate environment consistently bombards us with a superfluity of stimuli, this ordinary consciousness distills the humming, buzzing confusion around us down to that which serves our survival (Time-Life 106). Something as simple as crossing the street requires ignoring ninety-nine percent of the sights, sounds, and smells that surround us (Shulgin).

While awareness may be shifted so as to bring these ignored yet perhaps somehow useful stimuli to attention, our culture perpetuates a powerful and peculiar ideology in which the ordinary, waking state of consciousness is the *only* necessary and valid state. Thomas B. Roberts, of the University of Northern Illinois, refers to this as the “singlestate fallacy” and suggests that we instead consider states of consciousness as being to the mind what applications are to computers. Remaining forever in the waking state is like having access to a computer’s many applications but only ever using that computer to word process (Thomas Roberts 69-70).

Allowing that the map is not the terrain, the following evolutionary model of consciousness derives from Robert Anton Wilson, who drew from Sigmund Freud, C. G. Jung, Timothy Leary, and Carl Sagan (Wilson, *Prometheus*). Whereas Wilson's model assumes that human beings are genetically equipped with eight neurocolloidal circuits, or layers of mind, I simplify by using only five.

The first layer, our reptilian survival circuit, is hundreds of millions of years old. Our most powerful program, distributed among the amygdala, hippocampus, and adrenal gland, this circuit hard-wires us for maternal attachment and fight-or-flight response. Very early in life and due largely to chance circumstance, the child imprints either info-filia or info-phobia. That is, we become powerfully predisposed to see either a world that is essentially safe and interesting or a world that is terrible and frightening, although most fall somewhere between the two ends of this spectrum. Some psychologists argue that autism, incidence of which has increased three-fold within the past twenty years, is a genetically predisposed and environmentally imprinted condition wherein the outside world appears so horrible that the individual retreats into the safety of the self (Centers for Disease Control; see also Wilson, "Techniques").

We share our second circuit, centralized in the thalamus and cerebellum, with fellow mammals; this circuit wires in pack affiliation and ego-territoriality, emotion and the politics of submission and domination. With activation of this circuitry, the child begins to test his or her status in the family hierarchy. Those who take their heaviest imprinting on this circuit approach personal interactions as contests to be won or lost (cf. Schwartz). Freud called this layer the *anal stage*, averring to toddlers seeking pleasure through control of their bowel movements. According to Jamie Glowacki, an expert in the field of potty training, children over the past ten to fifteen years have experienced greater than ordinary problems in learning how to use the toilet, due, she argues, to our quickening pace of life and increasing levels of anxiety (Glowacki 146-150).¹

With the intersection of the first and second circuits, the bio-survival unit extends beyond the mother figure to the larger nexus of tribe, kin, or nation-state. Just as the feudal political economy linked the bio-survival of peasant to lord, the capitalist political economy links the bio-survival of the working class to an employing class wielding control over access to food, shelter, medical care, education, and all other things that money affords.

The third circuit, symbolic-verbal rationality, situated in the frontal cortex, is unique to humanity and thrusts us into history. The ancient Greeks spoke of this circuitry as the faculty of mind attuned to linear time that produces and possesses truth. Synonymous with instrumental reason, this circuitry, called the *ratio* in the Middle Ages, is the source of Newtonian science, a. k. a. the plumbing level of reality, and the modern idea of progress (Pieper 28). According to Wilson, the first-and-third-circuit binary constitutes the basis for the essential dialectic of history: over time, communication intensifies and information spreads, which threatens ruling elites who react with inquisitions and other varieties of repression ("Techniques").²

When activated, first-circuit consciousness and its attendant stress chemicals are notoriously capable of overpowering the rational mind. As Edward Herman and Noam Chomsky illustrated in *Manufacturing Consent*, advertisers and politicians regularly rely on fear to advance consumerism, war, and other logical absurdities. Fear, goes the Bene Gesserit litany from Frank Herbert's *Dune*, is the mind-killer. Reason, declaimed Martin Luther, is a whore (Whitford).

Working in dialectic with the third circuit, the fourth circuit, associated with morality and tribal taboo, functions as an evolutionary brake by sanctioning thought and action. In particular, local cultural taboos define for us with whom it is permissible and impermissible to mate. Typically, by our early thirties, the worldview inherited from and suited to the circumstances of our local culture will harden and set for life, in effect dooming us to a certain blindness regarding the greatest portion of the surrounding ontological plenum. In this sense culture is both home and prison. Thus leaving one's local reality, in one way or another, outwardly or inwardly, is indispensable to breaking its spell.³

Beyond reason and morality, there appear higher levels of consciousness notoriously resistant to language and yet indispensable to the progress of civilization. Throughout history, virtually all world cultures have recognized the powers of a few special, highly realized beings: Moses, Christ, Buddha, Mohammad, Theresa of Avila, and countless others — men and women able to see, intuit, and dream in uncanny ways. The ancient Greeks identified this circuitry, called the *intellectus* by Medieval scholars, with the faculty of mind attuned to the eternal present that receives and becomes possessed by truth, associated variously with intuition, wonder, grace, spiritual vision, *gestalt* perception, and the pineal gland (Pieper 28). Known as *dhyana* in the East, meaning “the trance of unity,” this state of consciousness brings ego dissolution, enhanced compassion and sensitivity to others, including plants, animals, and works of art (Mirante; see also Zigler 164).

While expressions of fifth-circuit consciousness would seem historically to emerge spontaneously and rarely, a vast majority of the world's cultures appear to ritually occasion its rapture. In her 1973 study of 488 world cultures, Erika Bourguignon found that 437 practiced one or more ritual forms of consciousness-raising. Although her sample primarily included non-state societies, institutionalized elevation of consciousness appears to play a significant role in the foundation of Western culture.

Each autumn from roughly 1400 B.C. into the Christian era, thousands of pilgrims traveled to the temple of Demeter to be initiated into the central mystery of Greek civilization, considered to be the culminating experience of a lifetime. Following months of spiritual preparation and ingesting *kykeon* — a sacred potion likely featuring barley ergot — devotees would awaken to the rapture of the *intellectus*, revealing a world of beauty, terror, and wonder, and dissolving boundaries between self and other. Dedicating themselves to the cultivation of this faculty, members of the Athenian leisure class

established *skole*, which in the Greek, properly speaking, does not refer to “school,” but to *leisure* (Pieper 19).

Relieved from the daily struggle of earning one’s bread, these “founders of Western culture” — Pericles, Herodotus, Hippocrates, Aristotle, Euripides, Phidias, and many others — re-envisioned and re-created themselves through the arts of Politics, History, Medicine, Philosophy, Poetry, Comedy, Sculpture, etc (C. L. R. James; see also Wasson, Hofmann and Ruck). Pieper remarked upon the transcendental nature of their endeavors:

Because Wholeness is what man strives for, the power to achieve leisure is one of the fundamental powers of the human soul. Like the gift for contemplative absorption in the things that are, and like the capacity of the spirit to soar in festive celebration, the power to know leisure is the power to overstep the boundaries of the workaday world and reach out to superhuman, life-giving existential forces that refresh and renew us before we turn back to our daily work. Only in genuine leisure does a “gate to freedom” open. (50-51; see also 22-23 and 57)

Through the Middle Ages, cycles of rituals and feasts institutionalized a shifting of the window of consciousness from the corporeal to the cosmic, from harvest time to dream time, and from daily toil to divine worship. Inhabiting these “two minds” remained essential to achieving a fully human state of being, apprised of its divine nature and place in the larger order of existence. Over the past centuries, however, the world of work has infiltrated and eroded these sacred spaces “with such a velocity,” warns Pieper, that we may speak of it as a “demonic force in history” (53). “Construction of a civilization that knows little or nothing of these deeper realities can only make things worse” (Pieper 11).

2. The Phenomenology of Capital

Settle the economic question and you settle all other questions. It is the Aaron’s rod which swallows up the rest.

William Morris, *Factory Work as It Might Be* 5

When economics is the dominant factor, once again we will bring down everything to the level of survival,,, It is the laws of the jungle again — the survival of the fittest.

Sadhguru Vasudev, “Allowing the Feminine to Flower”

Joseph Campbell once said that you can determine a society’s state of consciousness by looking at its urban skyline (Campbell and Moyers). Standing today in any major downtown, one sees financial institutions looming above church towers and state capitol buildings, an image indicative of the economic order overshadowing the religious and political. A peculiar form of economic consciousness lies deep within our cultural DNA.

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An archaeological dig into the depths of the modern mind might take us to the records of early contacts between the conquistadors and indigenous Americans. Following his initial encounter with the native Arawaks, Columbus wrote in his journal:

They willingly traded everything they owned. They do not bear arms, and do not know them, for I showed them a sword, they took it by the edge and cut themselves out of ignorance.... They would make fine servants.... With fifty men we could subjugate them all and make them do whatever we want. (Qtd. in Zinn 1-2)

Welcoming him as their returning god, a Quetzalcoatl, the Arawaks offered Columbus gifts of gold, which he mistakenly assumed to be plentiful in the land. Massively indebted to Queen Isabella of Spain, the sailor demanded ten pounds of the precious metal from each native. As they returned to him empty-handed, he punished their non-compliance by chopping off hands and watching the victims bleed to death. Seizing the next-most valuable commodity available, the sailor loaded the Arawaks themselves onto his ships and hauled them across the Atlantic to be sold as slaves.

Had Columbus been receptive to those he encountered, he may have wished to learn and live among them. More sensitive observers of the New World recognized the natives' humanity and lamented their demise: "Endless testimonies," wrote Bartolome de Las Casas, "prove [their] mild and pacific temperament.... But our work was to exasperate, ravage, kill, mangle and destroy" (qtd. in Zinn 6).

Whereas the actions of the conquistadors and colonizers may be perceived as devilish and immoral, they are better understood as traumatic clashes of competing moral imperatives. These men were not simply cold-blooded psychopathic killers, but, as David Graeber contends, men caught in webs of greed and shame, driven by the frantic urgency of debt repayment on interest-bearing loans that was added to the righteous indignation of having to owe anything after enduring such a perilous journey (Graeber 317-318). Blinded to the Arawaks' humanity by the morality of debt, Columbus and his men could see only commodities to be turned into money

Five hundred years later, under and surrounding our urban skyscrapers, temples to money, roughly one hundred and fifty million fellow Americans, or half the population, live paycheck-to-paycheck while another hundred million enjoy less than six months of financial cushioning (Hazen). Considering the cosmic duality of mind and matter, widespread insecurity regarding basic needs — food, shelter, safety — ensures that general anxiety and first-circuit vigilance maintain a steady grip on the body social, significantly limiting neurological activity associated with receptive awareness.

As a 2013 study of poverty's effect on IQ concluded, "the all-consuming fretting" that comes with poverty can cost a person as many as thirteen IQ points. Rather than suggesting that the poor are stupid, the British-American team determined that precarious living limits "mental bandwidth" in a way that is comparable to losing an entire night's sleep. "The poor are often highly effective at focusing on and dealing with pressing problems," remarked Eldar Shafir, professor of psychology and public affairs at

Princeton University. “But they don’t have leftover bandwidth to devote to other tasks” (qtd. in Kelland). “Poverty is bleak and cuts off your long-term brain,” wrote Linda Tirado in a 2014 essay. “It doesn’t leave you much room to think about what you are doing, only to attend to the next thing and the next. Planning isn’t in the mix.”

Economics is widely misunderstood in our society due to the enduring ontological framework of the Western Enlightenment. Whereas Newtonian philosophy draws us to see discrete *objects* and *individuals*, modes of production are better understood through a language of *processes* and *relationships*. Instead of seeing the economy as a way of producing *things*, we could look at it as a mode of producing *forms of consciousness* and *modes of associated living*.

During the Age of Enlightenment, the rise of capitalism coincided with the ascent of Reason. Voltaire beheld commercial societies and saw them as weaned from the fanaticism of religious war. According to Georg Hegel, markets brought together diverse cultures and oriented individuals to the needs and concerns of each other. Hegel concluded, as did Adam Smith, that the new economy fostered a calculative attitude that freed the human spirit by weakening the hold of tradition and making individualism possible in fantastic new ways (Muller 139-165).

Among these novel virtues, however, critics began to spot forms of psychic and cultural degradation. The rational being birthed by the market revealed itself to be part human, part monster. Observing the frenetic bustling of the French marketplaces, Friedrich Engels described “a horde of ravenous beasts (for what else are competitors?) who devour one another.”

Although the calculative mentality engendered by market societies appeared to weaken the stranglehold of ecclesiastical authority, critics charged that it threatened to subordinate all other attitudes and modes of thought. Max Weber, Werner Sombart, and György Lukács all cautioned that technical thinking and narrow focus upon means would obstruct the ends to which those means contribute (see Muller 240-241; 257; 263-271). Instrumental rationality, warned Martin Heidegger, might ultimately eradicate the “meditative thought” — those refined thoughts, perceptions, and emotions arising through contemplation and reflection — that is the very essence of our humanity (Carr 222).

In their 2011 publication *Lost in Transition*, Christian Smith and colleagues from Notre Dame University explained that millennials increasingly navigate ethical propositions based only on time, feeling, benefit, and desire. Concepts such as virtue, morality, and justice, prevalent throughout much of Western history, were non-considerations (Fleet; see also Lyon). One can see throughout contemporary society the ghastly consequences of calculative reason applied to situations where it does not righteously belong. Pharmaceutical companies suppress studies warning of their medicines’ lethal effects; automakers withhold vital safety features from cars and trucks; oil and gas companies hide research indicating that fossil fuel consumption is rending the biosphere (Dowie 18-32; Hyde 62-64; Goodman and Nissen; Carrington and Mommers). Although it might

tempt to label the actions of corporate executives in such cases as corrupt and immoral, it is more instructive to consider the actors as abiding to the peculiar laws and moralities of the institutions they serve. Nonetheless, these men and women, incapable of recognizing their connections with and responsibility to others, exhibit a careless, immature humanity.

3. The Neurochemistry of Capitalism

*We are so close to the world of work that we can't see what it does to us.
We have to rely on outside observers from other times or other cultures to
appreciate the extremity and the pathology of our present position.*

Bob Black, "The Abolition of Work"

Mirroring its architecture, a society's state of consciousness is reflected and shaped by its choice of drugs. Our language often misleads us to believe that the self possesses an essence independent of what it ingests; but we are not merely persons who "take" drugs; we are neurochemical organisms in which drugs become active parts, living through us as we live through them.

Writing in 1998, Marshall Sahlins illustrated caffeine's indispensable contribution to the development of the industrial economy, which required workers to be productive for many hours a day beyond innate biorhythms. Beginning with only a small, two-hundred-pound-a-year sample of Chinese tea in the mid-1600s, the English were, a century later, importing two million pounds annually, and up to twenty million by the turn of the nineteenth century. Tea quickly became "an indispensable necessity of life" (J. L. Cranmer-Byng, qtd. in Sahlins 418) and "the god to which everything else was sacrificed" (E. T. Pritchard, qtd. in Sahlins 418).

According to Zygmunt Bauman, *attention* itself has become the principal limit to capital growth in the information age, as societies appear, consciously or not, to be seeking ways to push physiological boundaries. Franco Berardi goes so far as to argue that the "irrational exuberance" of the 1990s was due in large part to millions of workers in Silicon Valley "consuming tons of cocaine, amphetamines, and Prozac." When the supply of these drugs was cut off and removed from the workers' neurochemistry, the bubble burst. The years since have witnessed an explosion in the licit market for coffee, energy drinks, B12 shots, and other attention-preserving stimulants (sometimes explode).

Although attentional disorders have been recognized since at least the turn of the 20th century, it was not until the 1980s and 90s that doctors regularly prescribed children and adolescents powerful drugs — Ritalin and Adderall — to treat Attention Deficit Disorders. In an April 2015 edition of the *New York Times*, Alan Schwarz reported that the first generation of Americans to grow accustomed to taking amphetamines as study drugs in college had graduated and carried the habit into the workforce. Adults are using the drugs not to get high, writes Schwarz, but to get hired. One financial industry source told him, "Friends of mine in finance, on Wall Street, were traders and had to start at five

in the morning on top of their games — most of them were taking Adderall. You can't be the one who is sluggish." Asked about her own habit, the worker testified:

I did my job faster than anybody. I was on a mission, and I was not going to stop until I succeeded and got what I wanted..... It's like this at most of the companies I know with driven young people — there's a certain expectation of performance And if you don't meet it, and I'm not really worried how, someone else will. (Qtd. in Schwarz)

The *proletarian*, argues Bernard Stiegler, beyond simply a worker, is one who has been reduced to a functional unit of an economic system, denied agency and denuded of *savoir-vivre*, i.e., knowledge of how to live. Capital's war to proletarianize consumers and producers, he writes, exerts powerful pressure upon technological and phenomenological becoming (*States of Shock* 128). Whilst increasing and intensifying work-focus capacity, caffeine and other stimulants may simultaneously arrest what Karl Polanyi referred to as *subsidiary awareness*. Polanyi argues that comprehension of certain phenomena, such as those dealt with in history, philosophy, and religion — essentially the Humanities — often requires one to *de-focus* the mind, allowing details and explicit parts to recede into the background so as to perceive larger patterns. "Unbridled lucidity," he wrote, "can destroy our understanding of complex matters" (qtd. in Zigler 164). Our attentional bandwidth liquidated through daily economic warfare, we are left to consult outside observers as to the present condition of our being.

Hailing from the Amazon Rain Forest, mother of all the world's forests, Davi Kopenawa, a Yanomami shaman, travels to the modern world to raise awareness about the destruction of his home at the hands of loggers, prospectors, and cattle ranchers. Versed in reconciling the local and the global, the infinitesimal and the infinite, Kopenawa draws firm connections between the despoiling of the Amazon and the lives of those he calls the "white people." Visiting New York City, financial capital of the planet, he sees men and women entranced by a love of merchandise and deaf to the spirits who plead on behalf of the forest (Kopenawa and Albert 375-377).

Impressed by the ingenuity of their architecture, Kopenawa nonetheless observes that the white people, tormented by their work and money, "only see their wives, their children, and their merchandise when they sleep. They must anxiously think about their work and their trips. In the din of their cities," he continues,

multitudes of people moved very fast and in every direction, like ants. They started one way and turned around, then went the other way. They looked at the ground all the time and never saw the sky.... People there live piled up one on top of each other and squeezed side by side, as frenzied as wasps in their nest. It all makes you dizzy and obscures your thought. The endless noise and the smoke covering everything prevent you from thinking right. This is probably why the white people can't hear us!. The lives of white people who hurry around all day like ants seem sad to me. They are always impatient and anxious not to get to their job late or be thrown away. They barely sleep and run all day in a daze. They

only talk about working and the money they lack.... [T]he babble of televisions and radios cover all the other voices. White people are always worried because of all this racket through which they hurry all day. Their hearts beat too fast, their thought is seized with dizziness, and their eyes are always on the alert. I think that this endless noise prevents their thoughts from joining together. It is so. In the end, their thoughts become scattered and fixed at their feet, and this is how you become stupid. (Kopenawa and Albert 349; 354-355).

Leaving the heart of nature for the epicenter of the global order, Kopenawa finds himself immersed in a toxic mental environment. Consumed by the struggle to survive and “make it” in this world, and suffering twin epidemics of stress and lack of sleep, thought reduces to reflex (Daily Mail Reporter). From the vantage point of the rain forest shaman, we appear something less than fully human.

4. The Net

Evil is that which makes for separateness; and that which makes for separateness is self-destructive.... Conversely, the qualities which have led to biological progress are the qualities which make it possible for individual beings to escape from their separateness — intelligence and the tendency to co-operate. Love and understanding are valuable even on the biological level. Hatred, unawareness, stupidity and all that makes for increase of separateness are the qualities that, as a matter of historical fact, have led either to the extinction of a species, or to its becoming a living fossil, incapable of making further biological progress.

Aldous Huxley, “Beliefs” 350

Save for the alphabet and the printing press, the Internet may be the single most powerful mind-altering technology that has ever come into general use.

Nicholas Carr 116

Two generations ago, Marshall McLuhan recognized that all tools are essentially prosthetic. In other words, human beings change themselves through the creation and incorporation of tools into their lives. Automobiles extend the powers of our legs; radios extend the reach of the voice and ear; clothing extends the protective functions of skin and hair. More than all other types, McLuhan insisted, communications technologies transform the human world (McLuhan, *Understanding Media*). Two and a half thousand years ago, spread of the phonetic alphabet spurred the rise of empires, along with the academic tradition of Plato and Aristotle. Five hundred years ago, the printing press gave rise to the Protestant Revolution, the nation state, the Western Enlightenment, Science, the Industrial Revolution, and the modern school. Once again, at the dawn of the 21st

century, we appear to be in the midst of seismic changes, both curative and toxic, resulting from a revolution in our communication technology.

With the advent of the digital age, McLuhan envisioned a global village in which physical distances ceased to serve as barriers to human connection. Such a new “electronic information environment,” he wrote, “compels commitment and participation. We have become irrevocably involved with, and responsible for, each other” (*The Medium is the Massage* 12). In only the past decade, folks around the world have utilized digital communications technologies to break through the de-facto censorship of corporate and state media to raise awareness of injustice (love translated to the public sphere) and spark political movements, from Black Lives Matter to Occupy Wall Street and the Arab Spring. In the wake of natural disasters, we have seen citizens organize relief efforts in the absence of aid from governmental agencies, autonomously directing food, shelter, and physicians to areas of greatest need (Smolan). And yet, we may ask whether our newfound connectedness has in fact brought humanity any closer together, and in so doing contributed to the love and understanding side of Huxley’s spectrum. One could argue that we have thus far, in the third millennium, moved farther apart from one another and closer to self-destruction.

Perhaps our problem is the same one that Neil Postman saw in Huxley’s *Brave New World*: “Huxley feared,” wrote Postman in *Amusing Ourselves to Death*, “those who would give us so much [information] that we would be reduced to passivity and egoism” (qtd. in Andrew Postman). As both Nicholas Carr and Bernard Stiegler argue, caring and critical consciousness — the combination of emotion and reason that we need in order to deal intelligently with the world — require focused, undistracted attention; but these are neither native to our species nor encouraged by our habits of digital media use (Stiegler, *Taking Care*).

Human beings evolved short, distractible attention spans through thousands of generations of life in environments where we survived by attuning ourselves to subtle changes of light and sound, a moving shadow or the snap of a twig alerting us to either predator or prey. What we today refer to as “thought” emerges from cultural traditions (and likely the mastery of fire) that train the mind away from its inherent distractibility (Carr). Most humans are “reason-able,” writes Stiegler, meaning that we are capable of acquiring the intellectual and attentional prowess requisite for both citizenship and mature personhood. Attainment of these faculties by the masses, Stiegler argues, has been the *raison d’être* of the modern school. However, this project has fallen under heavy assault by the consumer programming industries. Guided by experts in the field of psychology and informed of the intricacies and intimacies of our lives, these agencies seek to destroy reason in order to render us infantilized consumers, incapable of self-authorship (Stiegler, *States of Shock*).

Over the past decade, a growing weight of psychological and sociological research has found that our habits of digital technology usage are re-wiring the mind and altering the dynamics of our relationships. While digital media present us with unprecedented opportunities to cultivate socialized intelligence and critical consciousness, we appear to

be using them in ways that weaken the mental faculties that would allow us to seize these opportunities. Socialized intelligence and critical consciousness, writes Carr, “emerge from neural processes that are inherently slow” (220). Yet the more time that we spend with digital technology, the faster our internal clocks move.

Jonathan Sweller, an Australian educational psychologist, explains that the human capacity to wrestle with complexity, essentially “intellectual prowess,” is a function of “schemas” that develop out of long-term memory, which is not just a storehouse of information but also the seat of problem-solving and understanding (Carr 124-125). People become “more intelligent” when information initially perceived in short-term memory becomes incorporated into long-term memory, where it augments our schema. By ingesting information slowly and steadily, such as in undistracted book reading, this process transpires efficiently and effectively.

However, our tendencies while reading on screens are to do so not in steady, focused ways, but instead by scanning, skimming, and jumping from page to page. By bombarding ourselves with stimuli — hyperlinks, news-feeds, pop-ups, and message alerts — we overload working memory, so that new inputs continually push information out of the mind before it can be assimilated into our schema (Carr 139-143).

Mounting research demonstrates that increased demands upon working memory blunt our critical and empathic functions. For example, although we can instantaneously empathize with others whom we witness suffering physically, the mental operations required for appreciating the psychological and moral dimensions of emotional suffering unfold slowly. While smart phones and other digital devices extend our abilities to locate, categorize, and assess, they carry the danger of short-circuiting those processes that allow us to understand and care (Carr 220-221).

5. A Thought Experiment

It is only necessary to ask a few questions as to the progress of the articles of commerce from the fields where they grow, to our houses, to become aware that we eat and drink and wear perjury and fraud in a hundred commodities.

Ralph Waldo Emerson, “Man the Reformer,” qtd. in Warnick 95

Here manual labor is drudgery and toil is slavery. The men cannot possibly find any satisfaction in their work. They simply work to make a living. Their sweat and dull pain are part of the price paid for the fine cars we all run. And most of us run the cars without knowing what price is being paid for them.

Reinhold Niebuhr 65, after a visit to a Detroit auto factory (1929)

Three centuries ago, Enlightenment thinkers hoped that markets would bring together citizens of the world and orient each to the needs and concerns of others. Since that time, technological progress has re-made the planet not so much into a global village, but more accurately into a global marketplace. Yet my relations to others through the market remain largely invisible.

Commodity fetishism refers to the phenomenon whereby we endow inanimate objects with metaphysical properties to the effect of concealing human relationships, so that I see shoes and tomatoes as *things* and not as products of human labor. This, as Marx recognized, is the lynchpin of our economic system. Our entire mode of life, he believed, relied upon our failing to come to consciousness about the elemental facts of human interconnection.

It stands to reason that if I could see past the commodity form to the human relationships that it conceals, then the commodity might be de-mystified and lose its power over me. The Internet offers a substantially heightened capacity to peer behind the veil and bear witness to our interconnection, beautiful or ugly as it may be. Hypothetically, I could behold the conditions of food and garment workers at factory farms and sweatshops, revealing the suffering that is so often invested into the things I purchase. Theoretically, this could cause me to change my behaviors in such a way as to reduce injustice. Analogously, in the days following the 2015 Paris attacks, news networks depicted not only images of carnage, but also the names and faces of victims and their loved ones. We learned that they were college students, musicians, or fathers. We heard their stories and instinctively empathized (Lam and Alexandra). On some level, they were us and we were them, and we sent our prayers across the ocean.

However, as Jeremy Scahill highlights, there are daily massacres in the Middle East — at wedding parties, funerals, hospitals, etc. — in which we are complicit and yet of which we remain unaware. Each month, according to monitoring groups such as Airwars and the Syrian Observatory for Human Rights, American tax dollars contribute to the deaths of scores of innocent civilians, including women and children. We fund their killing and the weapons that kill them, and we never know their stories; they remain nameless and invisible (see Goodman, Gonzalez, Scahill, and Greenwald; see also Rachel Roberts and Goodman and Beckerle).

What difference might it make to know as much about “the others” as we know about “our own”? What if, as Amy Goodman wondered in her 2014 I. F. Stone Lifetime Achievement Award acceptance speech, our media served as “a huge kitchen table that stretches across the globe, [where] we all sit around and debate and discuss the most important issues of the day: war and peace, life and death? That, I believe,” concluded Goodman, “is what will save us” (Goodman). Still, the question remains whether or not our awareness would make any difference. Following Marx, Reinhold Niebuhr argued that personal, embodied contact is an indispensable ingredient of human ethics. We cannot, Niebuhr believed, treat others justly (lovingly) when we fail to connect on this basic, eye-to-eye level.

Writing about digital media since the 1980s, professor and psychoanalyst Sherry Turkle of M. I. T., for decades optimistic about the direction of communications technologies, observes a troubling correlation between digital connectivity and a coarsening of human relationships. Turkle contends that although our 21st-century media have allowed us to remain connected across vast geographical distances, they have also enabled us to sustain the kind of lifestyle in which typical Americans work longer hours, increasingly feel that they “have no time,” live away from family, belong to no religious or civic associations, and report feeling more insecure, isolated, and lonely than ever (Turkle 157).

Although we may treasure the efficiency that digital media afford, this efficiency can prove toxic when it encroaches upon personal relationships. Rapid communication over physical distance has, Turkle argues, supported a growing tendency in our culture toward psychoanalytic narcissism: not self-love, but “a personality so fragile that it ... cannot tolerate the complex demands of other people but tries to relate to them by distorting who they are and splitting off what it needs, what it can use” (177). Skyler Wang, a sociologist who uses and studies online dating services, describes what he sees as “relationshopping,” a turn toward objectification and commodification of potential mates, away from the thrilling and arduous journey of building a relationship (Roman). Depriving ourselves of the messiness that accompanies embodied affection, we risk losing what we need to become mature persons in touch with our human depths.

6. Toward a Curriculum of Consciousness

In Nekhlyudov, as in all people, there were two men; one the spiritual man, who sought his well-being in such matters only as could at the same time do other people some good, and the other the animal man, who was looking out only for his own well-being, ready for it to sacrifice the well-being of the whole world. During that period of his insanity of egotism, induced by his Petersburgian and military life, the animal man was ruling within him and had completely suppressed the spiritual man. But, upon seeing Katyusha and becoming actuated by the same feeling which he had had for her before, the spiritual man raised his head, and he began to assert his rights.

Leo Tolstoy, *Resurrection* 78

Suddenly you notice, that there aren't these separations, that we're not on these separate islands shouting across to someone else and trying to hear what they're saying and misunderstanding. You know, you used the word yourself, 'empathy'. This thing's flowing underneath, we're part of a single continent. It meets underneath the water. And with that goes such delight. The sober certainty of waking bliss.

Gerald Heard circa 1955

“The young,” said Helen Mirren in her May, 2017 commencement address to graduates at Tulane University, “carry intrinsically within them the energy and idealism that will regenerate human life on this planet as it hurtles through time and space.” Mirren shared that her own youthful search for meaning through the tumult of the 1970s led her to an ancient Mayan word now tattooed on her hand: *Inlakesh*, meaning “you are my other self; we are one; and *we are all in this together*.” These are the timeless truths of our common humanity, she concluded, that the rising generation must somehow realize and bring to bear upon the crises and opportunities of the 21st century (Mirren). Parallel to Huxley’s spectrum of good and evil, *inlakesh* offers a useful litmus for gauging the phenomenological quality of our society and imagining a curriculum that might assist the young in the work of self-transcendence.

The economic, neurochemical, and technological facets of life contribute to an ontological pharmacology of being and becoming. At present, we appear to inhabit a toxic phenomenological ecosystem that simultaneously reflects and contributes to the degradation of social and biological systems. Nonetheless, if these lenses prove useful in describing our circumstances, they may also reveal signposts toward a healthier curriculum of consciousness, a phenomenological *pharmakon* of political economy, neurochemistry, and digital technology.

For many centuries, alphabetic *hypomnemata* — writing, the study of scripture, the library of the Humanities, science, and the Republic of Letters, the free press and informed public opinion — have constituted a western grounds of *savoir-vivre*: systems of care, knowledge of right living, avenues to individuation, the forging of a unique self (Stiegler, *States of Shock*). Still in the morning hours of the digital revolution, we find that our educational embrace of our newfound tools has proven either minimally-discriminate or outright addictogenic. We remain in search of a pedagogy by which to inoculate ourselves against the behavioral control techniques of the consumer industry and re-arrange our inherited literary hypomnemata into more democratic digital forms.

Historically, American culture has surrounded major events of adolescents’ technological becoming with rituals and rites of passage. For example, we invest significant time in teaching young people about the practical and ethical dimensions of using a firearm, driving a car, or encountering drugs and alcohol. Such efforts promote what the Greeks called *melete* or *epimeleia* — discipline, solicitude, care. We can find similar practices related to digital technology in South Korea, for instance, where educators have wrestled with the travails of the digital age for perhaps a decade longer than have we here in the United States. South Korean elementary teachers counsel that the first lessons of Internet usage must be ethical. Hallways feature signs and students recite songs intended to instill conscientiousness regarding the humanity on the other side of the screen: “I am the Internet guardian angel. I will be the first to protect. I want to be the first to protect. Though faces are unknown, it’s a warm neighborhood. Precious Internet friend. Friend! Netiquette!” (Dretzin).

In recent decades, interest has grown among American educators in “mindfulness,” a practice which, rightly interpreted, draws from Zen Buddhist practices to assist children

and adolescents in distilling attention, clearing the mind, and opening the heart (Rempel). Amidst rising levels of stress, anxiety, and depression among youth, studies have found that incorporation of yoga, meditation, breathing exercises, and Tai Chi into the school day can lead to increases in neurological activity associated with empathy, compassion, and self-awareness, enabling students to see beyond their own frame of reference (Hölzel et al.; see also McFadden, Sandler, and Fieldstadt, and also Meiklejohn et al.). Such healthier states of mind promise to enhance the benefits of digital connectivity and offer prophylaxis against its ills.

Pursued further, “mindfulness” and other spiritual practices issue variously from millennia-old traditions of training youth to recognize and tame first and second-circuit demons — the Mr. Hyde residing in us all. As the pupil progresses to higher levels, learning to exercise third and fourth-circuit control over first and second-circuit impulses, bandwidth is opened for expression of fifth-circuit awareness.

For the entirety of its existence, our species has shaped and changed itself through the use of tools, organic and inorganic. Anthropologists and psychologists attest that *psychedelics* — which translates as “mind-manifesting” — have the capacity to assist in revealing aspects of reality erstwhile veiled by waking consciousness. Currently, and following a half-century inquisition, university laboratories are resurrecting investigations into psychoactive compounds — also known as *entheogens*, or “plant teachers” — such as psilocybin, ibogaine, ayahuasca, ketamine, and others, which have variously been found to assist men and women in the work of self-revision, including recovery from trauma or addiction, strengthening connection to nature, and preparation for death (Wilson, “Techniques”; see also Kupferschmidt, and also Heyes and Carlander). “There’s something at its core,” says Roland Griffiths of Johns Hopkins University,

that has to do with the core of moral and ethical behavior, about the sense of interconnectedness of all people and things. We’re talking about love and caretaking for other people and for the environment. And we have the opportunity to study that. I can’t imagine anything more important than that. (Qtd. in Shulgin)

Mystics such as Ram Dass, formerly Dr. Richard Alpert, who pioneered psychedelic studies at Harvard University along with Timothy Leary, claim that psychedelics are unnecessary and potentially detrimental shortcuts to what can be achieved through spiritual devotion and instruction from a competent practitioner. A problem with Ram Dass’ position might be that the traditional methods of enlightenment — Ram Dass himself traveled to the Himalayas and spent years studying with a yogi, drawing water, cooking rice, and meditating — are highly inaccessible to the beleaguered inhabitants of this toxic consumerscape.

Like any other tool, psychoactive drugs are *pharmaka* and can be used to either curative or poisoning effects; thus they require a healthy balance of positive and negative liberty: both the freedom and prudent wisdom to structure one’s own neurochemistry. It may on one hand be useful to recall that entheogens have played significant contributory roles in

a number of the 20th century's great accomplishments: Francis Crick credited LSD with helping him discover the structure of DNA; Paul Erdos, perhaps the most prolific mathematician to have ever lived, insisted that amphetamines were indispensable to his process; Carl Sagan advocated marijuana as an aid to thinking (Gonzalez). At present, however, toxic economic and phenomenological circumstances appear to condition much drug use, giving rise to national and global health crises. Improving our chemical and digital pharmacology will go hand-in-hand with making basic security and leisure more widely available in society.

Since the late-18th century, philosophers and economists have argued that an income guaranteed to satisfy the fundamental needs of all could dramatically transform society. In a world lifted from a fear economy, every man and woman could entertain the question that Robert Anton Wilson attributes to Buckminster Fuller: "What was it that I was so interested in as a child before I was told that I had to earn a living?" The answer, Wilson suggests, coming from millions and then billions of souls liberated from drudgery, would make the Renaissance look like a Greenwich Village art show and the Enlightenment like a high school science fair (Wilson, "RICH" 148). This year, Finland began its first experiments providing citizens with an income guaranteed to meet their basic needs. Cities in the Netherlands, Italy, Scotland, and Ontario are also moving towards their own trials with the citizen's wage, of which almost seventy percent of European Union residents now approve (Henley).

Currently tasked with sorting winners and losers, haves and have-nots, our schools remain in the business of proletarianizing the young. Relieved of this loathsome burden, one can imagine what a school or university might look like: a true institution of leisure, where none are crippled by the urgency of debt repayment or compelled to approach their education as preparation for a job, and all may feast on the treasures of our collective human heritage as artistic, intellectual, and spiritual beings.

Among other things, our Promethean labor entails mastery of our economy, neurochemistry, and digital technology. Regarding pedagogies of transcendence, Aldous Huxley suggests that *nothing short of everything will really do*: spiritual devotion and sacred mushrooms and meditation and study and leisure — *no one thing alone* — will all play vital roles in maintaining a healthy phenomenological ecosystem (Huxley, *Island*). Our educational tradition passes through the midwife Socrates, killed for attempting to push others through the labor pains of *digenes*. Although the horizon at the precipice of the end of history appears dark, perhaps it will prove to be the darkness not of the tomb but of the womb (Kaur).

Notes

¹ These trends are corroborated in academic literature; cf. Farrell and Barrett.

² As a contemporary example of the effect of this trend, federal prosecutions of whistleblowers have surged in the digital age. See Greenberg and Mian. Also, according to the watchdog group Mapping Media Freedom, the past decade has seen a spike in the incidence of intimidation and murder of journalists (McChrystal).

³ This was the advice of my undergraduate academic advisor, the late Steven Rubenstein. Programs of intercultural exchange and study abroad, which more students than ever are taking advantage of, often contribute to the opening of worldviews and expand appreciation for global humanity.

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